

Playford, G., González, F., Moreno, C., Alansari, A. (2008). Palynostratigraphy of the Sarhle Series (Mississippian), Jebilet Massif, Morocco. *Micropaleontology*, 54 (2), 89-124

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Abstract:

The Jebilet Massif, located in the southern part of the Moroccan Western Meseta, includes a sequence known as the Sarhle Series, which comprises mostly black shales with subordinate volcanic rocks and hosts several massive sulfide deposits. Hitherto, the Sarhle Series has received only scant biostratigraphic attention. Accordingly, a detailed palynological analysis of the shaly Sarhle strata that embrace the massive sulfide deposit of Draa Sfar, ca. 20km north of Marrakech, is presented herein. The palynoflora consists predominantly of moderately well preserved miospores, together with quantitatively subordinate marine palynomorphs (acritarchs, prasinophyte phycmata) and scolecodonts. The miospore content, documented systematically herein, comprises 19 genera including 29 species, five of which (*Cristatisporites mixtus*, *Densosporites dissonus*, *Indotriradites immutabilis*, *Vallatisporites extensivus* and *Endoculeospora marrakechensis*) are newly established. The Sarhle miospore assemblage closely resembles those reported from late Viséan-early Serpukhovian strata elsewhere in North Africa and adjacent regions. Some similarities are also evident with Western Gondwanan assemblages (viz., from the Parnaíba, Solimoes and Amazonas basins of northern Brazil). The palynological data, in conjunction with published faunal evidence accrued from the overlying lithostratigraphic unit, demonstrate that the age of the black shales of the Sarhle Series hosting the Draa Sfar sulfide deposit can be constrained to the late Viséan (Asbian); this, moreover, is corroborated by radiometric determinations from associated volcanic rocks.

Key words:

Palynology, Asbian, Viséan, Jebilet Massif, Morocco